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Comparative evaluation of anti-uplift strategies and deformation control measures in cut-and-cover station construction

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Abstract. This study utilizes the Zhong Yi Road Station foundation pit project of Wuhan Metro Line 12 as a case study to develop a numerical model via Plaxis3D finite element software. The research explores the influence of various construction stages on diaphragm wall horizontal displacements, ground surface settlements, and differential settlements between diaphragm walls and lattice columns, with a comparative analysis against the open-cut method. Furthermore, the effects of base slab thickness and overlying soil layer thickness on buoyancy-induced deformations of the station's main structure are systematically examined. The results reveal that horizontal displacements of diaphragm walls and ground surface settlements increase progressively with excavation depth. In contrast, differential settlements between diaphragm walls and lattice columns demonstrate a fluctuating pattern. In abundant groundwater surrounding the foundation pit, buoyancy after water level recovery considerably influences diaphragm walls, ground surface settlements, and the station's structural integrity. The base slab thickness most affects the station's vertical deformation due to buoyancy, where greater slab thickness leads to substantial reductions in deformation. Compared to the open-cut method, the cut-and-cover approach exhibits better efficacy in managing foundation pit deformations and minimizing disturbances to the surrounding environment. Nonetheless, the maximum deformation is located closer to one side of the pit. Optimization strategies for the cut-and-cover method are proposed to serve as valuable references for similar projects.

Keywords. Foundation pit, Cover excavation, Numerical simulation, anti-buoyancy.

1. Introduction

The construction of urban subway stations takes place in densely built-up areas, where foundation pit excavation may cause damage to existing structures, including surface settlement, building damage, diaphragm wall uplift, and failure of supporting systems, leading to engineering safety incidents [1, 2]. In China, the construction of subway systems has evolved from open-cut excavation methods to various contemporary techniques, such as sequential excavation and shield tunneling, greatly accelerating the rapid development of the country's metro infrastructure. However, due to the considerable excavation depth, excessive deformation of foundation pits remains a critical issue in ongoing research. Previous studies have indicated that shield tunneling causes less deformation of foundation pits compared to open-cut excavation, yet the underlying mechanisms of these deformations remain unclear. The buoyancy stability issue is particularly critical for subway stations

[3].

Regarding the deformation of foundation pits for subway stations using shield tunneling and open-cut excavation methods, Guo Yangyang et al. [4] conducted a study based on the foundation pit engineering of Qingyangguan Station on the Chengdu Metro. Their research demonstrated that the combined construction method of open-cut and shield tunneling can enhance the support stiffness by using a cover slab, effectively controlling the deformation of the support structure and surface settlement. Tao Lianjin et al. [5] employed FLAC3D simulations to model the Changchun Railway Station South Plaza Transportation Hub's construction process under shield tunneling and sequential excavation. Their findings concluded that shield tunneling is superior to sequential excavation in controlling the deformation of underground structures. Ding Zhigang et al. [6] utilized Plaxis analysis software to investigate the impact of different foundation pit construction methods on surrounding settlements. They organized and analyzed deformation monitoring data around the pit, concluding that shield tunneling in urban foundation pit construction offers significant social and environmental benefits.

Regarding the buoyancy stability of subway stations, Zhou Siyuan et al. [7] performed buoyancy calculations on the unique structure of an Israeli metro station using numerical simulations and theoretical calculations and compared these results with Chinese design standards. Xue-Yan Liu et al. [8] employed the limit equilibrium method to study tunnel uplift resistance and proposed models and formulas for calculating buoyancy in underground structures. They provided an improved approach for predicting tunnel uplift resistance based on the mechanism of dilatant failure. Hang Chen et al. [9] applied numerical analysis methods to design buoyancy resistance for ultra-large and ultra-deep underground structural foundations, analyzing the feasibility and cost-effectiveness of combining buoyancy piles with buoyancy anchors in underground structures.

In summary, prior research on cut-and-cover foundation pits has paid limited attention to differential settlements, which are crucial for assessing the feasibility of the cut-and-cover reverse construction method. In underground structural engineering, conventional anti-buoyancy measures—such as tension piles, waterproof curtains, and structural self-weight—are predominantly applied in open-cut foundation pit projects. In contrast, studies on anti-buoyancy mechanisms specific to cut-and-cover stations remain scarce. This study employs a three-dimensional model developed in Plaxis3D finite element software to investigate the impacts of various construction stages on diaphragm wall horizontal displacements, ground surface settlements, and deformation patterns, with a comparative analysis against the open-cut method. Furthermore, optimization strategies for cut-and-cover foundation pits are explored, along with a parametric investigation into the effects of buoyancy on the structural integrity of the main station structure. The findings offer valuable insights for similar engineering applications.

2. Project Overview

This study analyzes the Zhong Yi Road Station of the Wuhan Metro, designed as a three-story underground frame structure. The station's main construction employs the cover-excavation reverse method, with a comprehensive support scheme integrating both the support structure and the main structure. The thickness of the diaphragm wall is 1.5 m, with an embedded depth of 52.0 m and no internal supports. The longitudinal spacing of the main structure is 8.50 m. The station's main structure and the diaphragm wall are constructed using C35 concrete.

Separate cross-sections were selected for the station's deformation control comparison and buoyancy resistance analysis to minimize potential errors. The cross-section at monitoring point ZQT82 (5-5) was chosen for the deformation control analysis, while the cross-section at Q7B07 (8-8) was selected for the buoyancy resistance analysis. The profile diagrams for these two cross-sections are shown in Figure 1, and the soil layer parameters for each section are provided in Table 1.

Figure 1 Typical profile 8-8 indicates the distribution of structures in the pit

Table 1. Parameters of soil layers

soil	$\rho(\text{g/cm}^3)$	$c(\text{kPa})$	$\varphi(\circ)$	E_{50}^{ref}	$E_{\text{oed}}^{\text{ref}}$	$E_{\text{ur}}^{\text{ref}}$	m
Miscellaneous fill	1.82	6.00	12.00	8000	8000	24000	0.80
Silty clay	1.88	13.00	23.00	9000	9000	27000	0.80
Silty fine sand	1.93	0.00	30.50	11000	11000	33000	0.80
Pebble	2.00	1.00	24.00	12000	12000	36000	0.80
Strongly weathered rocks	2.34	110.00	25.00	30000	30000	90000	0.80
Medium weathered rocks	2.45	220.00	31.00	30000	30000	90000	0.50

3. Numerical Simulation Analysis

3.1. Numerical Model Construction

A three-dimensional finite element model was constructed using the finite element software Plaxis 3D based on the actual engineering conditions. Since the model boundary is approximately three times the excavation depth from the pit, the model size for the analysis of excavation-induced deformation control is $35 \text{ m} \times 160 \text{ m} \times 80 \text{ m}$. The open-cut excavation method used a corresponding model with the exact dimensions as a control group. The model size for the buoyancy resistance analysis of the station is $250 \text{ m} \times 35 \text{ m} \times 80 \text{ m}$, as shown in Figure 2. The soil material is modeled using the Hardening Soil Model (HSS) to ensure computational accuracy. The diaphragm walls and the upper temporary support structures are modeled as plate elements. The main structure's wall panels are modeled using soil elements, while the lattice columns and lower pile foundations are simulated using embedded piles. The construction conditions are summarized in Table 2.

Figure 2. Numerical model

Table 2. Excavation conditions

Analysis step	Cover-digging method	Open excavation	Anti-floating analysis
Phase 1		Ground stress equilibrium	
Phase 2		Diaphragm wall and lattice column construction	
Phase 3	Excavate to the top plate	Construction support 1	Excavate to the top plate
Phase 4	Construction of the top plate	Excavate 1	Construction of the top plate
Phase 5	Backfill and open to traffic	Construction support 2	Backfill and open to traffic
Phase 6	Excavation of the center plate	Excavate 2	Excavation of the center plate
Phase 7	Construction of the center plate	Construction support 3	Construction of the center plate
Phase 8	Excavation to the base	Excavate 3	Excavation to the base
Phase 9	Construction of the base plate	...	Construction of the base plate
Phase 10		Construction support 3	Reset Displacement
Phase 11		Excavate 3	Restoration of the waterline

3.2. Model Adaptability Analysis

This study establishes a three-dimensional finite element model based on the Wuhan Metro Line 12 Zhong yi Road Station excavation project to compare and analyze the differences between the cover-excavation method and the open-cut excavation method, as well as to investigate the impact of buoyant forces on the excavation. Before conducting the parameter analysis, an adaptability analysis of the model was performed by comparing actual monitoring data with simulation results to verify the reasonableness of the model parameter settings. Deformation data from the diaphragm wall at the monitoring point in the cover-excavation method excavation were extracted for comparison, as shown in Figure 3. As shown in the figure, the simulated and measured values of deep horizontal displacement of the diaphragm wall in the left graph correspond well with similar trends. In the right graph, the numerical model's maximum displacement and corresponding depth are 36.28 mm and 27.00 m, respectively, while the measured values are 35.73 mm and 27.60 m. The depths are similar, but the numerical model shows a slightly larger displacement. This discrepancy may be due to the fact that the surrounding soil had not fully released strain energy during the excavation phase at the time of monitoring, causing the recorded displacement at the monitoring point to be smaller. This validates the reasonableness of the model parameter settings, confirming that the model is suitable for further analysis.

Figure 3. Measured and simulated values at ZQT82(left) and Q7B07(right) monitoring points

3.3. Analysis of Numerical Calculation Results

To investigate the stress-deformation behavior of the excavation under different cover-excavation conditions, deformation data at various construction stages were extracted, as shown in Figure 4. Analysis of Figure 4(a) reveals that as the excavation progresses, the horizontal displacement of the diaphragm wall gradually increases, with the depth at which the maximum displacement occurs shifting downward. Further analysis of the horizontal displacement of the diaphragm wall reveals that the deformation increment induced by the excavation stage mainly occurs below the completed slab, with no significant displacement above the slab. This is primarily due to the construction sequence in the cover-excavation method, where the slab is poured first, and excavation proceeds only after the slab reaches the design strength. The slab, made of reinforced concrete, possesses high strength and integrity, effectively limiting the deformation of the diaphragm wall above it. As excavation progresses, surface settlement gradually increases, which is consistent with the trend observed in the diaphragm wall displacement. The primary influence zone of surface settlement induced by excavation is approximately 0-56 m from the excavation edge, about twice the excavation depth. The secondary influence zone is roughly between 56 m and 75 m, approximately 2.7 times the excavation depth.

The horizontal displacement of the diaphragm wall at the bottom of the excavation is shown in Figure 4(b). It can be observed that the horizontal displacement of the diaphragm wall under the cover-excavation method is similar to the typical deformation observed in open-cut excavation, with the deformation increasing gradually during the excavation stages and exhibiting an overall "inward-convex" pattern. The maximum displacements are 12.89 mm, 22.13 mm, and 36.28 mm, respectively. Unlike open-cut excavations, the diaphragm wall deformation above the main structure's top slab is relatively tiny. This is because the soil above the top slab was backfilled before the excavation of the main structure, resulting in a relatively balanced soil pressure on both sides of the diaphragm wall, which minimizes its deformation. After the groundwater level is restored, significant changes in the diaphragm wall deformation are observed, with an overall deformation direction away from the excavation. This is due to the upward pressure on the base slab of the station structure caused by buoyant forces, which subsequently affect the deformation of the diaphragm wall on both sides of the station's side walls. The diaphragm wall in the lower part of the station is directly affected by buoyant forces, resulting in a more considerable deformation. Analysis of the surface deformation data at different excavation stages reveals that as the excavation progresses to the base slab of the station, surface settlement gradually increases, similar to the surface settlement observed in typical open-cut excavation. Due to the extensive excavation cross-section and depth, the primary influence zone for surface settlement is within 0-40 m from the excavation edge, after which the deformation gradually decreases. As the water level is restored to its natural state, the surrounding soil around the excavation rises upward. This deformation is attributed to the lateral compression of the soil towards the excavation during the excavation phase, which causes surface settlement. After the water level is restored, the buoyant force causes the soil to rise, leading to deformation patterns distinct from those observed during excavation.

(a) Cover-digging method

Figure 4 Deformation diagram of foundation pit under different working conditions

4. Parametric analysis of station anti-buoyancy mechanisms and comparison with the open excavation

4.1. Parametric analysis of station anti-buoyancy mechanisms

In the absence of specialized anti-buoyancy designs, the station's buoyancy resistance is primarily derived from the weight of the superstructure and the frictional forces between the structure and the surrounding soil. Consequently, the station's buoyancy resistance is predominantly influenced by parameters such as the contact area between the foundation piles and the soil and the thickness of the overlying soil layer above the structure. The structural component most susceptible to buoyancy effects is the base slab of the main station structure. Accordingly, this study takes the thickness of the overlying soil layer and the base slab as independent variables, with the vertical deformation at the slab-soil interface as the dependent variable, to evaluate their influence on the structural buoyancy resistance.

Figure 5 illustrates the vertical anti-buoyancy deformation patterns of the base slab as influenced by variations in its thickness and the thickness of the overlying soil layer. The overall deformation of the base slab exhibits a “larger at the center, smaller at the edges” pattern between central columns. Deformation is most pronounced near the central columns, followed by the areas near the diaphragm walls at the ends, and least in the central region of the slab. An analysis of the maximum vertical deformation reveals a negative correlation between slab thickness and deformation, as the thickness varies incrementally from -30% to +30%. This finding indicates that greater slab thickness significantly improves the anti-buoyancy performance of the base slab. The underlying causes of this deformation are attributed to the enhanced anti-buoyancy capacity associated with increased slab thickness. On the one hand, the increased thickness enhances the slab's bending resistance, effectively mitigating deformation under buoyancy forces. On the other hand, the additional material thickness slightly increases the gravitational effect, which is relatively minor compared to the improvement in bending resistance.

The vertical deformation of the base slab was analyzed under varying thicknesses of the overlying soil layer. During excavation, temporary supports were installed at 2-meter intervals and removed during the backfilling process. An increase in the thickness of the overlying soil layer corresponds to a continuous reduction in the vertical deformation of the base slab. The decrease in deformation is attributed to the gravitational effects of the thickened overlying soil layer, which, upon water table restoration, strengthens the station's overall resistance to buoyancy. Moreover, the increased burial depth amplifies the lateral earth pressure and frictional resistance exerted on both sides of the station, thereby indirectly mitigating the influence of buoyancy forces.

Figure 5 Vertical deformation of base plate under the influence of different base plate thicknesses(left) and various thicknesses of upper soil cover(right)

4.2. Comparison with Open Excavation Construction Method

The horizontal displacement of the diaphragm wall and the surface settlement outside the excavation for both the open-cut and cover-excavation methods at the final excavation stage are shown in Figure 6. As shown in the figure, the deformation patterns of the diaphragm wall caused by both the open-cut and cover-excavation methods are similar, with a "concave" shape characterized by larger displacements in the middle and smaller displacements at the edges. The maximum displacement of the diaphragm wall induced by the open-cut method reaches 49.35 mm, which is generally more significant than that caused by the cover-excavation method. This is attributed to the use of the top slab of the main structure as the support structure in the cover-excavation method, resulting in a higher overall stiffness compared to the concrete and steel supports used in open-cut excavation. The increased stiffness of the cover-excavation method effectively mitigates the inward displacement of the diaphragm wall, making it superior to the open-cut method in terms of controlling the deformation of the supporting structure in this project. Further analysis reveals that the surface settlement deformation for both methods tends to exhibit a typical "trough-shaped" pattern. The maximum surface settlement induced by the open-cut method reaches -48.19 mm, slightly smaller than the deformation caused by the cover-excavation method. Upon examining the settlement curves, it is observed that on the left side of the "trough-shaped" deformation, the settlement induced by the cover-excavation method is more significant than that caused by the open-cut method. However, the cover-excavation method makes the settlement smaller on the side farther from the excavation. This indicates that the cover-excavation method is superior to the open-cut method in controlling the deformation of the surrounding environment.

In summary, through the comparative analysis of diaphragm wall deformation and surface settlement between the open-cut and cover-excavation methods, it can be concluded that the cover-excavation method outperforms the open-cut method in controlling the deformation of the surrounding structure and mitigating the impact on the surrounding environment. However, the deformation induced by the cover-excavation method is $0.23\%H$ (where H is the excavation depth), which significantly exceeds the specified value of 36.0 mm in the standards (with the maximum lateral displacement for Class I pits being $0.18\%H$ [10]). Therefore, servo steel supports [11] or a combined construction method is recommended for areas with strict deformation control requirements.

Figure 6. Foundation pit deformation diagram of two construction methods

4.3 Optimization Analysis of the Cover Excavation

Due to its distinctive construction technique, the cut-and-cover method significantly minimizes prolonged road closures during construction, facilitating rapid restoration of road traffic. Previous analyses have confirmed that the cut-and-cover method outperforms the open-cut method in most scenarios. In practical implementations of the cut-and-cover method, the roof or floor slab of the main structure typically functions as the primary deformation-resisting element. When the spacing between slabs is substantial, periods of unsupported conditions are inevitable, often resulting in excessive deformation of the retaining structure beneath the floor slab. Consequently, this section explores the addition of internal supports between slabs to limit the excavation height of each stage. The modified design is then compared with the original conditions to optimize the cut-and-cover construction scheme in Figure 7.

Figure 8 presents the maximum deformation of the diaphragm wall corresponding to varying excavation depths. As the excavation progresses, the maximum horizontal displacement of the diaphragm wall increases progressively with the excavation depth across all three schemes. Among the three schemes, optimize opinion b demonstrates the smallest increment in the maximum horizontal displacement of the diaphragm wall, measuring only 0.15%H. Optimize opinion achieves moderately effective deformation control, registering a value of 0.17%H. The control subject exhibits the least effective deformation control among the three schemes.

Further analysis of the maximum ground settlement under various optimization schemes reveals that diaphragm wall horizontal displacement and ground settlement trends are closely aligned. Optimize opinion b demonstrates the most effective deformation control, achieving a maximum ground settlement of -37.81 mm under the final excavation stage. Optimize opinion achieves moderately effective control, with a maximum ground settlement of -41.55 mm at the final excavation stage. The control subject exhibits the least effective deformation control among the three schemes. Compared to the excavation approach of the original scheme, Optimize Opinion B reduces the maximum ground settlement by 13.49 mm, corresponding to a decrease of approximately 26.29%. Optimize opinion reduces 9.75 mm in the maximum ground settlement, representing an approximately 19.01% decrease. A comparison of diaphragm wall deformation reveals that the variation in diaphragm wall horizontal displacement consistently exceeds that of ground settlement within the same construction scheme. This observation suggests that diaphragm wall deformation is more sensitive to construction schemes than ground settlement.

Comprehensive analysis reveals that further segmenting the floor slab's excavation steps will not eliminate the diaphragm wall horizontal displacement and ground settlement. Instead, it will cause them to converge towards a specific value. During construction, factors such as construction equipment and machinery should be considered, alongside a comprehensive evaluation of the segmental excavation height, to finalize the construction scheme.

Figure 7. Presents the optimized design schemes.

Figure 8. Comparison of excavation-induced deformations under various excavation schemes

Scheme A includes a single support between each floor slab. In contrast, Scheme B incorporates two supports per floor slab, evenly distributed vertically within the slabs, with a horizontal spacing of 3.0 m. The material specifications include $\phi 609 \times 16$ ordinary prestressed steel supports, with a prestress set at 300 kN. The conventional cut-and-cover method is employed as the control group for comparison, focusing on its differences in controlling the deformation of the retaining structure, ground vertical displacement, and other related factors.

5. Conclusion

This study is based on the excavation project of Zhongyilu Station on Wuhan Metro Line 12. It employs numerical simulation to investigate the effects of various construction stages on pit deformation compared to the cut-and-cover method. Finally, a parameter analysis of the anti-floating design for the main structure is performed, leading to the following conclusions:

(1) During cut-and-cover construction, the horizontal displacement of the diaphragm wall and ground settlement exhibit a progressively increasing trend as excavation proceeds, with uneven settlement observed on the surface. This phenomenon becomes more pronounced as the excavation depth increases. (2) When the surrounding groundwater around the station pit is relatively abundant, the buoyant force following water level recovery influences the diaphragm wall, the ground settlement around the pit, and the overall station structure, necessitating the implementation of corresponding anti-floating measures. The primary factor influencing structural anti-floating is the thickness of the station base slab. Its vertical deformation significantly decreases as the base slab thickness increases from -30% to +30%. (3) A comparison with the open-cut method reveals that the cut-and-cover method is more effective in controlling pit deformation and minimizing the impact on the surrounding environment. However, the maximum deformation occurs closer to one side of the pit. Based on this, an optimization of the cut-and-cover method is proposed, offering valuable insights for similar projects.

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